

Avonia quinaria

Red-flowered Avonia

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© K. Schade

Group: Eudicot

Size: 2-3 cm

Distribution:

Northern Cape province of South Africa, encompassing areas like Bushmanland and Northeastern Namaqualand.

Importance:

This succulent is an essential component of the diverse Karoo flora of South Africa. Its capacity to thrive in harsh, arid environments suggests a deep evolutionary history that merits further investigation. We can learn more about its adaptability and resilience from its genome.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 80.2 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 19.63 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 1.11 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.1% [Single: 93.9%, Duplicated: 5.2%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 27 198.08 kilobases

Contig number: 769

Sample Contributor contact details:

Dr Kedibone Masenya

South African National Biodiversity Institute/
University of Johannesburg

kedimasenya@gmail.com

DIPL**MICS**
CONNECTING RESEARCHERS & WORLD CLASS OMICS FACILITIES

Date Published: 2025-10-24

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17407168>

